

Studies in the Cotarnine Series. Part II. The Reactivity of the Aldehyde Group in Cotarnine and Benzoyl Cotarnines.

BY B. B. DEY AND (MISS.) P. LAKSHMI KANTAM.

The reactions of cotarnine with phenyl isocyanate and phenyl isothiocyanate studied in Part I (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 12, 885), depended on the activity of the secondary imino-hydrogen atom in cotarnine and thereby furnished evidence of the aldehydic structure for this base. We have now examined such reactions of cotarnine as involve the activity of the aldehyde group.

Cotarnine reacts smoothly with hydroxylamine yielding a crystalline derivative which should be considered to have the structure of an oxime (I, R' = H ; R = NOH), but may also be supposed to be derived from the tetrahydro-isoquinoline or carbinol form (II, R = NHOH)

(I)

(II)

The product readily yields di-acyl derivatives and interacts smoothly with two molecules of phenyl isocyanate, the resulting compound being identified with the product synthesised from cotar-nomethylphenylurea oxime and phenyl isocyanate (*loc. cit.*). These reactions clearly indicate the simultaneous presence of the oximino-hydroxyl group and of the secondary imino-hydrogen atom in cotarnine oxime and thus rule out Formula II. Again on reducing the oxime with sodium and alcohol, ammonia was found to be evolved and the product was identified as hydrocotarnine by the usual tests. This reaction can be easily understood if we assume that the reduction of the oxime to the amine is followed by the

elimination of ammonia from the amino and the secondary imino-groups and the consequent closure of the isoquinoline ring.

Further evidence of the activity of the aldehyde group of cotarnine is afforded by the ease with which this base condenses with aromatic amines such as aniline (Freund, *Ber.*, 1903, **36**, 1528) and the toluidines, anils being formed (I, $R = NPh$; $R' = H$).

These compounds are unstable and are decomposed quickly by alkalis, but they dissolve unchanged in cold acids and are recovered on basification. Attempts to prepare the benzoyl derivative of cotarno-*p*-toluidil with a view to identify it with the product obtained by the condensation of *p*-toluidine with benzo-cotarnine resulted in the production only of benzo-*p*-toluidide (m. p. 158°).

The reactions of cotarnine with benzoyl chloride (Roser, *Annalen*, 1889, **204**, 335) and with *o*-nitrobenzoyl chloride lend further support to the open chain aldehyde-imine structure. Of the two possible structures (I, $R = O$; $R' = CO \cdot Ph$.; II, $R = O \cdot CO \cdot Ph$) for the benzoylated product, Formula III has obviously to be accepted as correct on the following grounds:—

(a) It is quite insoluble in dilute acids showing that the neutralisation of the basic $N \cdot Me$ group by the benzoyl radical has taken place.

(b) It readily forms a crystalline monoxime which is soluble in cold alkali and which yields monoacetyl and monobenzoyl derivatives insoluble in cold alkali. The benzoyl derivative is found to be identical with the product of benzoylation of cotarnine oxime.

(c) It is oxidised by alkaline permanganate to benzoyl cotarninic acid.

(d) It condenses with aromatic amines with extreme ease yielding remarkably stable anils and toluidils (I, $R' = CO \cdot Ph$; $R = NPh$).

The stability of these compounds as well as of the anils and toluidils derived from cotarnomethyl phenyl urea is in striking contrast with the instability of the corresponding derivatives of cotarnine itself, and the difference should obviously be attributed to the presence of the mobile imino-hydrogen atom in the latter and its absence in the former. Once this hydrogen is removed and the basic function of cotarnine depressed either by acylation or by quarternary salt formation, the aldehydic group in the molecule seems to be released from its peculiar condition of bondage to the NH -group, resuming its activity and yielding the usual stable derivatives. The presence of the secondary imino-hydrogen in cotarnine and its absence in benzoyl

cotarnine and cotarnomethylphenylurea would thus account for the remarkable difference in the reactivity of the aldehydic group which is present in both these compounds.

The condensation of cotarnine with *o*-nitrobenzoyl chloride under the usual conditions gave *o*-nitrobenzoyl cotarnine (I, R=O ; R'=*o*-NO₂·C₆H₄CO) in excellent yield. In view of the proximity of the nitro- and the aldehyde groups in the molecule of this compound it was considered possible that the reduction of the nitro group would lead to the syntheses of interesting compounds and the subject is still under investigation.

Notwithstanding this accumulation of positive evidence of the occurrence of a reactive aldehyde group in the acylated derivatives of cotarnine, it has been observed that the latter do not enter into reaction with many compounds with which the aldehyde group of cotarnine itself condenses freely. Thus benzoylcotarnine does not condense with compounds containing reactive methylene groups such as resorcinol, phloroglucinol, malonic ester, nitromethane, etc., with which cotarnine easily reacts. Indeed, the condensation with nitromethane is quantitative and occurs so readily that it may serve as an excellent test for detecting traces of cotarnine. It is very probable that condensations of the latter type occur only with the carbinol form of cotarnine, the unreactivity of benzoyl cotarnine being explained by the impossibility of the formation of the carbinol phase in the latter. The acceptance of this view becomes all the easier when it is borne in mind that such condensations as those mentioned above are usually carried out in the presence of alcohol, a reagent which has been definitely shown to favour the change of the aldehydic into the carbinol form.

It will be seen that two structures are possible for the products of condensation of cotarnine with such compounds as acetone, acetophenone, *p*-aminoacetophenone, urea, phthalimidine, resorcinol and its monomethyl ether, nitroresorcinol, aromatic nitro-aldehydes, etc., all of which have been examined by us. They should be represented either as derivatives of 1-β-*N*-methyl-aminoethyl-2-benzaldehyde, if the cotarnine reacted in the aldehydic form, or as 1-substituted *N*-methyltetrahydroisoquinoline derivatives, the cotarnine reacting in the carbinol form:

Liebermann and Glawe (*Ber.*, 1904, 37, 211 2738) observed that a discrimination between the two structures might be made by such reactions as methylation or acetylation indicative of the presence or

absence of a hydrogen atom attached to the nitrogen. Attempts made by us to prepare such derivatives, however, have resulted either in the decomposition of the compounds into their respective components, *e.g.*, with anhydrocotarnino-carbamide and anhydrocotarnino-phthalimidine, or in the recovery of the original products. Anhydrocotarnino-*p*-amidoacetophenone provided the only exception in which a mono-acetyl derivative soluble in dilute acids was obtained by acetylation.

The condensation of cotarnine with *p*-amidoacetophenone may be expected to yield products having the following constitutions:—

(A)

(B)

(C)

(D)

The product was found to contain a free diazotisable aminogroup so that formulæ C and D have to be rejected. On treating with excess of acetic anhydride it formed only a monoacetyl derivative which dissolved readily in cold dilute acids. This clearly points to structure B as the correct one since a compound of Formula A should be expected to yield a diacetyl derivative insoluble in dilute acids. The general trend of the evidence obtained so far seems, therefore, to be in favour of regarding these products as 1-substituted tetrahydroisoquinoline derivatives,

EXPERIMENTAL.

Action of hydroxylamine hydrochloride on cotarnine: Cotarnine oxime (Roser, *Annalen*, 1889, 253, 335).—Roser refluxed the cotarnine solution with hydroxylamine for several hours. This we find to be unnecessary as the formation of the oxime takes place even in the cold. Cotarnine (2 g.) was suspended in water (20 c.c.), a solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1 g.) and sodium acetate crystals (2 g.) added and warmed on the water-bath when a clear solution was obtained. This was evaporated to about half the volume on the water-bath, cooled, and made alkaline with sodium carbonate and allowed to stand, when the oxime separated out almost quantitatively. Crystallisation from alcohol gave colourless rectangular plates, m.p. 157° (m.p. recorded in literature is 165-68°). The oxime dissolved in dilute alkali on warming slightly and was recovered on neutralising the liquid.

Phenylurethane of cotarnomethylphenylurea oxime.—Cotarnine oxime was suspended in dry benzene and treated slowly with the calculated amount of phenyl isocyanate. The oxime dissolved with evolution of heat and the product crystallised in the course of a few seconds, m.p. 151°, yield quantitative. It was identified with the compound obtained by the action of phenyl isocyanate on cotarnomethylphenylurea oxime (*loc. cit.* p. 840).

Cotarnomethylphenylthiourea oxime was prepared as above by the action of phenyl isothiocyanate on cotarnine oxime, the benzene solution being warmed on the water-bath for a few minutes. The product, m.p. 142°, was identified with the compound obtained by the oximation of cotarnomethyl phenyl thiourea (*loc. cit.* p. 842). As we have observed before, the phenyl isothiocyanate does not react with the oximino-hydroxyl group.

Benzoylated oxime of benzoyl cotarnine.—Cotarnine oxime (1.6 g.) was triturated in a mortar with 40 c.c. of N-NaOH and the opalescent solution treated in the cold with 2 c.c. of benzoyl chloride and vigorously shaken. The separated solid melted rather indefinitely (140°-50°). Two crystallisations from dilute alcohol gave colourless woolly fibres, m.p. 158°, quite insoluble in alkali. Admixture with benzoyl cotarnine oxime (m.p. 165°) depressed the m.p. to 140°. (Found: C, 67.55; H, 5.32; N, 6.6. $C_{26}H_{24}O_6N_2$ requires C, 67.82; H, 5.22; N, 6.1 per cent).

Acetylated oxime of acetylcotarnine.—Cotarnine oxime (1 g.) was treated with 10 drops of acetic anhydride, gently warmed and allowed

to stand for half an hour. It was then poured into water, the precipitate collected, washed and crystallised twice from dilute alcohol as soft colourless threads, m.p. 113° , insoluble in alkali. (Found: N, 8.51. $C_{16}H_{20}O_6N_2$ requires N, 8.33 per cent).

Reduction of Cotarnine Oxime to Hydrocotarnine

Cotarnine oxime (1 g.) was heated under reflux with absolute alcohol (30 c.c.) and sodium (2 g.) added in small pieces during one hour. Ammonia was copiously evolved and at the end of the reaction, the alcohol was mostly boiled off, water added and the oily product extracted repeatedly with ether. The thick reddish oil after distilling off the ether did not solidify easily. It was rubbed with a few drops of HBr solution when crystals of the hydrobromide of the base separated out. The salt was dissolved in the minimum quantity of water, basified strongly with caustic soda and cooled in ice when the hydrocotarnine separated out as colourless needles, m.p. 54° ; the hydrobromide (m.p. 224°) and the picrate (m.p. 173°) were prepared and identified with the hydrobromide and picrate of an authentic specimen of hydrocotarnine. The platinichloride of the base was analysed. [Found: Pt, 23.04. $(C_{12}H_{15}O_3N, HCl)_2 \cdot PtCl_4$ requires Pt, 22.9 per cent).

Condensation of Cotarnine with Aromatic Amines.

Cotarnine anil (Freund and Becker, *Ber.*, 1903, 36, 1527) has been prepared in quantitative yield by simply rubbing together molecular quantities of cotarnine (2 g.) and freshly distilled aniline (0.8 g.) in a mortar with a few drops of water. The oil solidified after some time. On washing with water containing a little hydrochloric acid it formed a colourless crystalline mass, m.p. 120° . (Found: N, 9.12. $C_{18}H_{20}O_3N_2$ requires N, 8.97 per cent).

Cotarnino-p-toluidil, m.p. $114-115^{\circ}$, was prepared in the same way. Attempt to crystallise it from hot alcohol led to decomposition into the components. Similarly on attempting the benzylation of the product under the usual conditions, needles, m.p. 158° , identical with benzo-p-toluidide, were obtained. (Found: N, 8.51. $C_{19}H_{22}O_3N_2$ requires N, 8.59 per cent) *Cotarnino-o-toluidil*, prepared in the same way, melted at 119° .

Benzoyl cotarnine was obtained by an improvement of the process described by Roser (*loc. cit.*). Cotarnine (2 g.) was triturated with N-alkali (20 c.c.) and benzoyl chloride (1 c.c.) in a mortar for 15

minutes when the oil solidified. The strongly alkaline solution was poured off, the solid rubbed well with water and dilute hydrochloric acid and then crystallised from hot alcohol as colourless prisms, m.p. 124°, yield quantitative. The product is very stable and is not attacked by dilute acids or alkalis even on warming.

Benzoyl cotarnine oxime was prepared in quantitative yield by mixing a hot alcoholic solution of benzoyl cotarnine (1 g.) with a concentrated aqueous solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.58 g.) and sodium acetate (1 g.). Colourless needles, m.p. 165°. On treating this with benzoyl chloride, the same product (m.p. 158°) as that formed by the benzoylation of cotarnine oxime was obtained.

The acetyl derivative of benzoyl cotarnine oxime was very easily prepared by the acetylation of the oxime in the usual way. It separated from alcohol in masses of soft threads, m.p. 152°. (Found: C, 63.1; H, 5.7; N, 7.3. $C_{21}H_{22}O_6N_2$ requires C, 63.31; H, 5.53; N, 7.04 per cent).

Benzoyl cotarnine azine, prepared in the usual way with hydrazine hydrochloride and alkali, crystallised from acetic acid in diamond shaped plates, m.p. 220°. (Found: N, 8.37. $C_{38}H_{38}O_8N_4$ requires N, 8.26 per cent).

Oxidation of benzoylcotarnine to benzoylcotarninic acid.—Finely powdered benzoyl cotarnine (1 g.), suspended in a solution of sodium hydroxide (2 g. in 50 c.c. of water) was refluxed with a 4% solution of potassium permanganate (0.308 g. in 8 c.c. of water) which was added slowly during half an hour. On cooling the filtrate some unchanged benzoyl cotarnine crystallised out. The yellow filtrate was saturated with sulphur dioxide, extracted thrice with ether and the white solid left on evaporation of the ether crystallised from dilute acetic acid. It formed a microcrystalline powder, m.p. 156°, dissolving in cold dilute sodium carbonate to a clear solution. The silver salt which was thrown down as a pale yellow precipitate from neutral solutions, was analysed. (Found: Ag, 22.9. $C_{19}H_{18}O_6N Ag$ requires Ag, 23.2 per cent).

Benzoyl cotarnine anil, prepared by Freund and Becker (*loc. cit.*), was obtained in an yield of 1.2 g. from 1 g. of cotarnine by rubbing the two bases with a little water and working up the resulting solid in the usual way. It was very stable and crystallised from boiling alcohol in small needles, m.p. 164°.

Benzoyl cotarnine-o-toluidil crystallised from alcohol in soft colourless needles, m. p. 150°. (Found: N, 6.5. $C_{26}H_{26}O_4N_2$ requires N, 6.5 per cent).

The *m-toluidil* and *p-toluidil* of benzoyl cotarnine; prepared by the same method, melted at 113° and 111° respectively. *Benzoyl cotarnine-p-phenetidil* was prepared by rubbing together benzoyl cotarnine (1 g.) with 10-12 drops of *p*-phenetidine, adding 4 c.c. of water and treating the separating oil with a few drops of dilute acetic acid, and crystallising the resulting solid from boiling alcohol. It separated in stellate clusters of needles, m. p. 135°. (Found: N, 5.83. $C_{27}H_{28}O_5N_2$ requires N, 6.08 per cent).

o-Nitrobenzoyl cotarnine was prepared from cotarnine and freshly prepared *o*-nitrobenzoylchloride by the same method as that used in preparing benzoyl cotarnine. It formed small prisms melting at 138°, sparingly soluble in alcohol and insoluble in acids and alkali. (Found: C, 58.6; H, 4.5; N, 7.31. $C_{19}H_{18}O_7N_2$ requires C, 59.06; H, 4.66; N, 7.25 per cent).

o-Nitrobenzoyl cotarnine oxime was prepared by suspending the nitrobenzoyl cotarnine (1 g.) in alcohol (6 c.c.) and adding a solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.5 g.) and sodium acetate (1 g.) in the minimum amount of water. On warming, a clear solution resulted and this was soon followed by the separation of slightly yellow prismatic needles, m. p. 193-94°; yield quantitative. (Found: N, 10.35. $C_{19}H_{19}O_7N_3$ requires N, 10.47 per cent).

o-Nitrobenzoyl cotarnine anil was prepared by rubbing aniline and the cotarnine in the usual way and then adding a few drops of dilute acetic acid. It was crystallised from a mixture of benzene and petroleum as small plates, m. p. 164°. It is very sparingly soluble in alcohol. (Found: N, 9.12. $C_{25}H_{23}O_6N_3$ requires N, 9.11 per cent).

Anhydrocotarnino-p-amido-acetophenone crystallised out on warming a solution of cotarnine (1 g.) and *p*-amido-acetophenone (0.6 g.) in absolute alcohol (12 c. c.) on the water-bath to 40° for 15 minutes and leaving overnight, m. p. 190-91°; yield 1.2 g. It is very sparingly soluble in the usual organic solvents but dissolves instantly in dilute acids and is reprecipitated on basification. (Found: C, 66.98; H, 6.25. $C_{20}H_{22}O_4N_2$ requires C, 67.79; H, 6.22 per cent).

The *monoacetyl* derivative, prepared in the usual way; crystallised in small needles, m. p. 105°. It dissolved unchanged in dilute acids to form a yellow solution. (Found: N, 7.29. $C_{22}H_{24}O_5N_2$ requires N, 7.07 per cent).

Anhydrocotarnino-carbamide (II, R = NHCONH₂).—Pure cotarnine (10 g.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol (60 c.c.) by gently warming and a solution of urea (2.8 g.) in the same solvent (50 c.c.) added

and the clear solution warmed on the water-bath for half an hour at a temperature not exceeding 45°. The urea derivative separated almost immediately on cooling as colourless prisms which were collected after an hour, washed with cold alcohol and dried; m. p. 182°, yield 11 g. The substance was insoluble in cold alcohol, ether, benzene, etc.; it dissolved in hot water but did not crystallise on cooling as it underwent considerable decomposition during the process. When a hot aqueous solution of the substance was treated with picric acid, cotarnine picrate (needles, m. p. 143°) crystallised out. A cold aqueous solution was found to have a pH of 7.7, *i.e.*, it was definitely alkaline. It dissolved instantly in cold dilute hydrochloric acid to a pale yellow solution and was recovered unchanged on basification after an hour. (Found: C, 55.3; H, 6.3. $C_{13}H_{17}O_4N_3$ requires C, 55.9; H, 6.1 per cent).

Anhydro-cotarninophthalimidine [II, R = C_6H_4] was

prepared in the same way as the urea compound, but the solid separated only on diluting the solution with water. It melted at 143-44° and was decomposed by boiling water. Cold dilute acids dissolved the substance unchanged. (Found: C, 67.77; H, 5.71, N, 8.13. $C_{20}H_{20}O_4N_2$ requires C, 68.19; H, 5.68; N, 7.95 per cent).

Anhydrocotarnino-resorcinol monomethyl ether separated as a cream coloured micro-crystalline powder, m. p. 221-22°, on warming the components in alcoholic solution to 40° and leaving overnight, yield quantitative. It is insoluble in ether and benzene, sparingly soluble in alcohol and very easily soluble in dilute acids. (Found: N, 4.27. $C_{19}H_{21}O_5N$ requires N, 4.08 per cent).

The condensations of cotarnine with the cresols (*o*-, *m*- and *p*-) and the naphthols (α - and β -) were tried without success.

Anhydrocotarnino-2-nitro-resorcinol, prepared in the same way from cotarnine and 2-nitroresorcinol crystallised in fine orange-coloured needles, m. p. 201°. Its properties were similar to those of the previous compound. It dissolved in cold hydrochloric acid and the sparingly soluble hydrochloride separated out almost immediately. (Found: N, 7.35. $C_{18}H_{18}O_7N_2$ requires N, 7.49 per cent. Found: Cl, 8.3. $C_{18}H_{18}O_7N_2, HCl$ requires Cl, 8.6 per cent).